

A Project Resource Management Study on Sustainable Development of SMEs in Nigeria

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Abstract

In this paper, a project resource management study on sustainable development of SMEs in Nigeria was investigated. This study hypothesizes that there is a positive impact of project resource management on sustainable development of SMEs in Nigeria. To verify the impact, this study adopts a survey research design to obtain information from 333 SMEs operators across 12 selected states spanning the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria through the distribution of structured questionnaire. Findings of the study reveal that the hypothesized positive impact of project resource management on sustainable development of SMEs in Nigeria is validated. Results further show that while having consultants as part of ensuring the integrity and effectiveness of a project is pertinent, a working project resource management plan remains an invaluable asset for attaining organizational goals. The findings are as follows. First, technological innovation capability has a positive effect on both business performance and organizational effectiveness. Second, organizational metacognition has a partial mediating effect on the effect of technological innovation capability on business performance and organizational effectiveness. The results suggest that chief executive officer (CEO) and middle managers contemplate the methodology of metacognition at the organizational level and that they should focus more on enhancing business performance by developing technological innovation capability and organizational metacognition.

Keywords: Project, Resource Management, Sustainable Development, SMEs.

Introduction

Entrepreneurs and managers of small businesses and firms are expected to possess a set of abilities known as managerial skills. According to [1], managerial skills are intended to promote a company's healthy growth rather than to include it in mortality figures for businesses. As a result of this, [1] assert that managerial competencies form a list of knowledge, skills and attitudes that are required for good business management and when combined, provide management with the necessary conditions to overcome obstacles, motivate

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the team and develop an organization's capabilities, and promote business success, regardless of whether they are essential or complementary management skills.

Human resource is the most important component in any organization to run the business it does [2]. Moreover, managerial skills can be viewed from a human perspective, concentrating on the skills necessary by managers, for instance by observing a potential behaviour by which managers exhibit their knowledge of the skill sets required by managers, or the synergy between their own abilities [2]. This view stems from the fact that a core component of the resource management process is people and once people are trained to man a given project, the set objectives of such projects are on the path of success.

In Nigeria, lack of entrepreneurial skills, strategic plan, business plan, managerial skills, adequate organizational set-up, succession plan, transparent operational system and the rest, are peculiar part of many founders and managers of SMEs [3]. This in turn is the reason many SMEs operators purchase obsolete and inefficient equipment thereby setting the stage of ab initio for lower level productivity as well as sub-standard goods. Moreover, the increasing pressures from the rapid changes occurring in the business environment have led to a variety of responses among organizations. Thus, project resource management is a proactive way of reducing such pressures [4].

There are assertions that businesses with formalized project resource management activities attain success than those with little or no regard to these for their business [5-6], thereby projecting the views of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. Nonetheless, a number of studies had attempted to examine the effect of resource management on sustainable growth of SMEs.

Looking from the dimension of the dynamic capacity of SMEs, it is often argued that their strategic direction has been robust. This posits that sustainability of SMEs can be enhanced with suitable project resource management tools like managerial training that enhances the work force [7]. This is because managerial training brings improvement to employee's skills, leadership with vision and not mafia managers will cap these suggested improvements [8]. Nonetheless, there are assertions that businesses with formalized project resource management activities usually achieve success than those with little or none for their business operations ([5-6]. This in turn enhances sustainable SMEs growth. However, it can be argued that the trend in developing economies where SMEs are largely run as family own businesses is responsible for the lack of sustainability of SMEs growth over the years. Overall, effective project resource management will enhance entrepreneurial strategic leadership while competing in turbulent and unpredictable environments [9-10]. In order to succeed and survive these turbulent business environments, entrepreneurs need to adapt to these environmental changes by means of strategic leadership. Evidently, project resource management has benefits that enhance the success of SMEs and must be considered by SMEs so as to achieve sustainable development. Thus, this study aims to investigate project resource management on sustainable development of SMEs in Nigeria.

Materials and Method

Research Question

This study is guided by the research question:

1. What is the effect of project resource management on sustainable development of SMEs in Nigeria?

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis guides this study:

H1: *There is a positive impact of project resource management on sustainable development of SMEs in Nigeria.*

Method

The study adopts a survey research design to obtain information from 333 SMEs operators across 12 selected states spanning the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria through the distribution of structured questionnaire. The data collected were analysed using partial least square structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) method.

Results and Discussion

Respondents Profile

According to the findings shown in Table 1, women make up 56.2% of the respondents, while men make up the remaining 43.8%. Regarding the respondents' age range, the findings showed that the majority of respondents (34.2%) were between the ages of 36 and 45, while (31.2%) were between the ages of 46 and 55 at the time the data was gathered. In terms of education, the majority of respondents (42.6%) held a bachelor's degree as their highest level of education as of the survey, followed by a diploma or NCE (26.1%) and a postgraduate degree (22.2%). Additionally, the study's findings show that 58.6% of respondents are both managers and business owners. Last but not least, the study's findings indicate that project team leaders make up the greatest proportion of respondents (71.5%), followed by project consultants (27.6%) and project team members (9%).

Table 1. Respondents' Profile

Categories	Frequency	Percent
Gender	333	100
Male	146	43.8
Female	187	56.2
Age Group	333	100
Below 26 years	30	9.0
26-35 years	62	18.6
36-45 years	114	34.2
46-55 years	104	31.2
Above 55 years	23	6.9
Education	333	100
Degree	142	42.6
Diploma/NCE	87	26.1
Postgraduate degree	74	22.2
SSCE or Equivalent	30	9.0
Industry	333	100
Agriculture	105	31.5
Construction	1	0.3
General Services	112	33.6
Manufacturing	4	1.2
Trading	111	33.3
Position	333	100

Both (Owner/Manager)	195	58.6
Manager	102	30.6
Owner	36	10.8
Role in Projects	333	100
Project consultant	92	27.6
Project team leader	238	71.5
Project team member	3	.9

Measurement of Variables

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

Prior to doing CFA analysis, the first EFA test was run to extract the factors for the factor analysis and structural analysis. The EFA was carried out multiple times using various combinations of all components and extraction techniques. The final EFA was ran to extract five (5) components underlying the 8 useable items using the Principal Component with Promax rotation and Kaiser Normalisation (see Table 2). According to the final EFA results shown in Table 2, the factors were extracted using the Bartlett's Test of Sphericity and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sample adequacy (about Chi-Square = 9151.183, degree of freedom = 253, $p < 0.001$). This demonstrates that the KMO value is greater than the 0.60 minimum threshold [11], demonstrating the usefulness of the factors and the suitability of the sample for the factor analysis. The significant value of Bartlett's Test ($p < .05$) also denotes that the correlational matrix is not an identity matrix and the data is good enough for further analysis [11].

All items have communalities over the permitted 0.50, which indicates how closely each item connects with all other items. Moreover, the findings indicate that the two variables together explained roughly 54.75% of the total variation (see Table 2). The EFA structure's variables were all kept.

Table 2. Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

FACTORS	PRem	SMEP	Extraction
Eigenvalues	11.438	1.153	-
Variance explained (%)	49.732	5.014	-
Cumulative (%)	49.732	74.700	-
PRem1		0.987	0.832
PRem2		0.775	0.790
PRem3		0.853	0.886
PRem4		0.648	0.819
PRem5		0.676	0.801
SMEP1			0.897
SMEP2			0.627
SMEP3			0.698
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy			0.928
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity		Approx. Ch-Square	9151.183
		Df	253
		Sig.	0.000

Keys: PRem- Project Resource Management; SMEP- SME Performance

Hypotheses Test Results

The H1 hypothesis was tested using the PLS-SEM bootstrapping approach (Table 3). From the table, the structural model estimates showed a significant positive association between project resource management and SMEs' performance (= 0.329, p-value = 0.000, t = 4.59, 95% CI = 0.197 to 0.477). H1 is therefore supported.

Table 3. Direct Effect of Project Resource Management Practice on SMEs Performance

Path	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	95% Conf. Interval		P Values	Interpretation
					Lower	Upper		
PRem -> SMEP	0.329	0.329	0.072	4.59	0.197	0.477	0.000	Supported

Importance of the Link between Project Management and Sustainable Development of SMEs

Results on the relationship between project resource management practice and SMEs' performance are presented. From Table 4, it can be inferred that project resource management was generally approved, therefore, the participants were in agreement that it is crucial to link project resource management to attaining sustainable development of SMEs (35.7%).

Table 4. Importance of the Link between Project Resource Management and Sustainable Development of SMEs

Statements	NI (%)	SI (%)	AI (%)	I (%)	VI (%)	Mean	Std. Dev.
How important is it to link project resource management to attain greater SMEs performance?	2.4	8.1	22.3	35.7	31.5	3.86	1.030

Note: NI = not important, SI = slightly important, AI = averagely important I = important VI = very important

Benefits of Project Resource Management to Sustainable Development of SMEs

Using descriptive statistics, the project resource management was evaluated. According to Table 5's findings, participants in the study, on average, strongly agreed (66.6%) that project resource management improves SME performance, lower project delivery costs, ensure increased profits for SME, increase SME project success rates, competitive advantage, and market share, guarantee customer expectations, ensure quality deliverables, and provide a clear understanding of project requirements, which in turn motivates staff. The participants agreed (47.5%) that SMEs' adoption and practice of project resource management results in high SMEs performance, with the engagement of project resource management specifically being assessed with a mean score of 3.61 (SD = 0.993) and increasing SMEs' performance. With a mean score of 3.76 (SD = 1.029), project resource management were also found to lower project delivery costs and guarantee higher profitability for SMEs.

This indicated that the participants generally (46.2%) agreed with the indicator that the adoption of project resource management by SMEs improves their performance. Additionally, it was discovered that project resource management techniques boost SMEs' project achievements, competitive advantage, and market share has a 3.76 (SD = 1.028) mean score. This demonstrated that the majority of participants (47.4%) agreed that SMEs project success stories are a result of the adoption of project resource management. Moreover, it was noted that the respondents (40.3%) felt that project resource management best ensures

client expectations. Due to effective project resource management techniques, SMEs report higher levels of customer satisfaction, with a mean score of 3.73 (SD = 1.056).

The results also reveal that project resource management guarantee high-quality deliverables, with a mean score of 3.69 (SD = 1.028), and the respondents were in agreement (47.5%) that this increased quality is reflected in the outputs from SMEs. With a mean value of 3.67 (SD = 1.049) by which the participants agreed (46.5%) that staff motivation contributes to greater performance of the SMEs, it was also discovered that project resource management give strong understanding of project requirements, which leads to staff motivation (view Table 5).

Table 5. Benefits of Project Management practices

Statements	SD (%)	D (%)	N (%)	A (%)	SA (%)	Mean	Std. Dev.
Engaging project resource management increases performance of SMEs	4.8	7.5	24.9	47.5	15.3	3.61	0.993
Project resource management reduce project delivery costs and ensures increased profits for SMEs	4.5	7.2	19.3	46.2	22.8	3.76	1.029
Project resource management increases higher degree of SMEs project successes, competitive advantage and market share.	4.5	7.5	18.1	47.4	22.5	3.76	1.028
Project resource management guarantees customer expectations.	4.2	8.4	22.5	40.3	24.6	3.73	1.056
Project resource management ensure quality deliverables.	5.1	7.2	20.7	47.5	19.5	3.69	1.028
Project resource management give good understanding of project requirement leading to staff motivation.	5.7	7.2	21.0	46.5	19.5	3.67	1.049

Discussion of the Findings

Effect of Project Resource Management on Sustainable Development of SMEs in Nigeria

The research objective poised to investigate the effect of project resource management on performance of SMEs in Nigeria. In order to attain this objective, hypothesis one (H₁) which asserts that there is a positive impact of project resource management on performance of SMEs in Nigeria was formulated. Results of the present study validate the hypothesized positive impact of project resource management on performance of SMEs in Nigeria. Findings also reveal that while having consultants as part of ensuring the integrity and effectiveness of a project is pertinent, a working project resource management plan remains an invaluable asset for attaining organizational goals [4,12].

In essence, the present study opines that while profit making remains pivotal for businesses, the challenging environment of doing businesses today has placed on SMEs managers the need for resource management [10, 13]. Moreover, the positive impacts of resource management on the performance of SMEs as seen from the investigated businesses give an obvious expression that SMEs employing project resource management stand a better chance of thriving in terms of business success and overall attainment of organizational goals [5, 12]. This assertion is in agreement with [3] who believed that the poor performance of SMEs in Nigeria is largely due to poor resource management. It is in this vein that [14] opined that SMEs need to ensure that they have the right competency set in situ in the early stages of their development. Additionally, the results show that there is a significant managerial support for resource management by

SMEs and they would invariably, leverage on this with the right environment in place. That is, the resource management processes within a firm are essentially dynamic in nature, rather than being static, thereby providing room for more competitive business strategy for success at the disposal of available resources in an ever changing business environment [15]. Evidently, H₁ is confirmed and supported.

Importance of the Link between Project Management and Sustainable Development of SMEs

From the results of the study, it is clear that by linking project resource management to SMEs operations, SMEs are positioned to attain business success. This agrees with previous studies [5]. Furthermore, findings of the present study show that the significance of linking project resource management and SMEs performance is irrespective of business size [13]. Hence, SMEs in Nigeria will be competitively positioned to thrive in today's world driven by best practices and technology transfer and as such, boosting the local economy in terms of job creation and promotion of export that SMEs have been known for globally (Adebayo Fashina et al., 2020). This aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs, Goals 1, 2, 3 and 8). Although government at various times and levels in Nigeria had made effort to boosting the SMEs sector with little success stories recorded, it is believed as can be inferred from the findings of this study that adequate implementation of project resource management in managerial decision and hiring of SMEs, will invariably help in attaining the goal of boosting the SMEs subsector for national economic recovery and job creation among others. For this reason, the formulated hypothesis was confirmed and supported while positioning SMEs for sustainable development in Nigeria.

Conclusion

To help SMEs contribute to the Nigerian economy, this study investigates the impact of project resource management on sustainable development of SMEs. An SMEs business can attain competitive edge from its effective use of project resource management practice. This keeps the business thriving in an increasingly unstable business environment experienced across different economies around the world in recent time. Nonetheless, project resource management is key to sustainable development of SMEs [7], and as such, SMEs could build long term approach to sustainability by incorporating project resource management in their business operations. The study presents a number of findings. The project resource management of SMEs is pivotal to sustainable development as it reinforces commitment to boosting the local economy in terms of job creation and export promotion of local goods. This contributes to the sustainability of nations through contributions from all for all (Goals 12 and 17). Furthermore, the study revealed that while having consultants as part of ensuring the integrity and effectiveness of a project is pertinent, SMEs should utilize a working project resource management plan as an invaluable asset for attaining organizational goals.

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